

Digital Appendix: Geology of Svalbard (SvalGEOL)

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This (digital) appendix of the “Geology of Svalbard: Deep-Time and Deep-Earth” report chapter in “The State of Environmental Science in Svalbard Report” (SESS) of the Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System (SIOS) contains relevant material, including complex tables, large-scale figures and digital data packages, summarised in the contents below.

Appendix element	Description	Where R = in printed report and digital D = digital only
Text A1	Full list of recommendations to SIOS	R
Text A4	Description of data packages	R
Table AT1	Overview of relevant online resources	R
Table AT2	Geophysical methods used to decipher the Earth’s various structures as a function of depth	R
Table AT3	Data sources for QGIS package presented as ADP1	D
Table AT4	Overview of relevant data repositories	D
Table AT5	SIOS Core Data and Geology	D
Table AT6	Comprehensive geoscientific data table	D
Figure AF1	Coverage map of data harvested as part of SvalGEOL	R
Figure AF2	Overview of fieldwork locations done by geologists according to RiS	D
Figure AF3	Diagram showcasing interdisciplinarity and interaction of all spheres	D
Figure AF4	Geoscience for future poster, linking geoscience professions to Sustainable Development Goals	D

Data package ADP1	QGIS data package including geophysical database (navigation only)	D
Data package ADP2	GPlates data package	D
Data package ADP3	Thermochronology data compilation (as an example for thematic geoscientific data harvesting)	D
Data package ADP4	Reference collection	D
Data package ADP5	Research in Svalbard (RiS) portal data used in Figure 2	D

Appendix 1 – Detailed list of recommendations

In the main report we have highlighted five main recommendations for how SIOS can assist the geosphere community, and integrate the geosphere more strongly into SIOS activities. Here we list these again, but with additional concrete goals that pave the way to reaching those. We recommend that SIOS:

- 1) Promotes the geosphere as a central and important element within the SIOS community through:
 - a) Inclusion of geosphere-themed sessions at key conferences (SIOS Polar Night Week, Svalbard Science Conference)
 - b) Support and promote geosphere-themed globally relevant international research projects in and around Svalbard, specifically scientific drilling under the auspices of the International Continental Scientific Drilling Programme (ICDP) and the International Ocean Drilling Programme (IODP and its successor IODP-3)
 - c) Continuing to consider the geosphere in SIOS-led infrastructure proposals (for instance for a national polar geophysical equipment pool or enhanced spatial coverage of GNSS stations including eastern Svalbard to quantify ongoing uplift)
 - d) Soliciting geosphere-themed SESS reports, specifically on the Quaternary, Evolution of life in Svalbard's record, seismicity, controlling factors on ongoing uplift and key geoscientific data types (e.g., geochemistry, geodetic data, sedimentary logs)
 - e) Including geosphere-themed elements in its outreach activity

- 2) Utilises its data management expertise to support the geoscientific community in Svalbard to make the heterogeneous geoscientific data FAIRly available through:
 - a) Providing transformation tools, workflows and resources for geologists to make geoscientific data compliant with SIOS-endorsed data portals
 - b) Providing recommendations on which repositories are suitable for storing and using various geoscientific data, considering aspects including the discipline's global preference, technical suitability and SIOS-interoperability
 - c) Consider extending the long time-series SIOS core data with more static regional geological data (e.g., digital outcrop models, photospheres, subsurface data)
 - d) Consider providing data services (e.g. visualisation) for FAIR-compliant geological data
 - e) Working actively with the Svalbard Science Forum to improve the post-fieldwork registration of metadata from geological campaigns
 - f) Optimising the interaction between global thematic geodatabases (Table AT4) and Svalbard portals (Appendix 2)
 - g) Soliciting data papers, perhaps through a SIOS-led special issue, on geoscientific topics such as palaeoclimate, sedimentary logs, geophysical (seismic, ERT, GPR etc.) data
 - h) Considering how unstructured data from centuries of geoscientific exploration of Svalbard can be made available and interoperable to the community
 - i) Influencing policy makers to work towards a user-centred Svalbard-wide geospatial data portal to enhance cross-disciplinary research

- 3) Takes an active role in adequate documentation, long-term storage and active re-use of physical material (i.e. rock samples, drill cores) by:
 - a) Re-vitalising the Svalbard Rock Vault concept with the relevant partners (UNIS, SNSK, NPI, NHM, NGU, Mining Commissioner, international partners) to provide a location for long-term storage and active re-use of physical material

- b) Working actively with the Svalbard Science Forum to enhance the capability of the Research in Svalbard (RiS) database to register sample metadata and sample physical locations
 - c) Providing an overview of the physical storage sites of geological objects from Svalbard, building on the efforts by the Svalbard Rock Vault initiative
- 4) Strives to transform “data” (geosphere-related and otherwise) into “products”, with societal or scientific relevance through:
- a) Conducting a questionnaire with key stakeholders on their knowledge needs and map this to existing competence clusters (e.g., depth to basement in Longyearbyen area, regional land uplift map)
 - b) Provide regularly updated geospatial data packages (with <https://qgreenland.org/> as a role model) to enhance relevant data usage and maximise cross-disciplinary research time
 - c) Organising hackathons linking the geoscientific and data analytics communities on clearly defined goals (e.g., automatic extraction of data from unstructured data sets like publications, reports etc.)
 - d) Considering how data can be best presented to society and the scientific community, with inspiration from www.climatearchive.org
- 5) Serves as a platform connecting the geosphere-community with other scientific communities by:
- a) Consider organising regular (user-funded) boat-based multidisciplinary expeditions to defined areas of Svalbard (reducing the environmental impact by joint logistics)
 - b) Enhanced focus on using existing SIOS’ tools like the aircraft for geosphere application (e.g., update the hyperspectral sensor with wavelengths suitable for bedrock geological mapping)
 - c) Be active in the development of large-scale geoscience projects leading up to the International Polar Year 2032-33

Appendix 2 - Overview of relevant online resources

Table AT1: Useful geoscientific online resources from Svalbard, including maps and data portals.

Resources	Comment	URL
Online resources (viewing mostly)		
GeoSvalbard	Geological maps (vector and images), selected cross-sections, sample and DOM locations	https://geokart.npolar.no/geologi/GeoSvalbard/
Svalbardkartet	Multi-disciplinary online portal including geology, an outdated claim map, national parks etc.	https://geokart.npolar.no/Html5Viewer/index.html?viewer=Svalbardkartet
TopoSvalbard	Topographic map including aerial imagery, old oblique aerial images	https://toposvalbard.npolar.no/
VRSvalbard	Photosphere-based atlas of Svalbard's geology	http://www.vrsvalbard.com
Svalbox	Digital outcrop models in the context of regional geology	http://portal.svalbox.no
Online resources (for direct streaming to GIS software and data download)		
Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI) geodata	Basemap services from NPI, including topography, satellite imagery and most layers as available on Svalbardkartet	https://geodata.npolar.no/
Svalbox	Digital outcrop models in the context of regional geology	http://portal.svalbox.no
Data portals		
BGR Arctic Repository	Data repository of Germany's Geological Survey (BGR) with an Arctic focus, including outcrop data and geophysical profiles	https://arctic.bgr.de/mapapps4/resources/apps/arktis/index.html?lang=en
AWI seismic profile map	The map will be linked very soon with the Pangaea database to directly access available profiles there. The navigation is not yet available that way.	https://maps.awi.de/awimaps/projects/public/?cu=geophysics_arctic#home
AWI sediment echosounder data	e.g., from cruises on RV Polarstern, RV Maria S. Merian, RV Heincke	Archived on PANGAEA, https://www.pangaea.de/?q=sediment+echo+sounding&maxlat=81.27311926447925&minlon=2.348750948196061&maxlon=33.63781344819606&minlat=76.88785354508799
NGU geodata portal	Data portal of the Norwegian Geological Survey	https://geo.ngu.no/geoscienceportalopen/Result?s?bookmark=0bf79eb071474cd7a92240d4360b84db
Norwegian Offshore Directorate data portal	Area is not open for petroleum exploration around Svalbard and seismic data are not available for open download	https://www.sodir.no/en/diskos/public-portal/

Appendix 3 - Geophysical methods of imaging different parts of the Earth's structure

Table AT2: Summary of the different geological and geophysical techniques used by geoscientists to infer the physical parameters of the Earth's internal structures and their surface expression. Ordered in roughly deep-to-shallow segments, noting that many processes cross domains over geological timescales.

Target interval	Indicative depth range (km) (focussed on continental domains unless otherwise specified)	Main geological and geophysical technique(s)	Comment	References
Lower mantle	~660 - 2890 km	Seismic tomography; Gravity/geoid	Structures include subducted slabs, mantle plumes, core boundary dynamics. Seismic data typically developed from global models. Limited resolution, coverage and sensitivity.	Jakovlev et al. (2012), Rickers et al. (2013), Panet et al. (2014), Gaina et al. (2014), Toyokuni et al. (2020a, b), Celli et al. (2021)
Upper mantle (including mantle transition zone)	~100-660 km Lithosphere-asthenosphere boundary (LAB) to base of the transition zone	Receiver functions of converted seismic waves, seismic tomography, gravity/geoid	Structures include subducting slabs, mantle plumes, mineral phase change in transition zones. Data limitations as for lower mantle.	Schaeffer and Lebedev (2013), Wilde-Piórko (2015)
Lithosphere-asthenosphere boundary (LAB)	~60-280 km under continents ~30-120 km under oceans	seismic, electromagnetic, petrological, thermal and gravity data	Major lateral variation from thin (12km) lithosphere at the mid-ocean ridge to 90-100 km beneath the Barents Sea	Klitzke et al. (2015), Minakov (2018), Grad and Majorowicz (2020)
Deeper parts of the crust and uppermost mantle	~20-100 km	wide-angle reflection/refraction seismic and seismological methods; Magnetotelluric data; Volcanic rocks (i.e. xenoliths)	Provides insights into electrical conductivity (i.e. fluid content)	Amundsen et al. (1987), Skjelkvåle et al. (1989), Ionov et al. (2002a, b), Griffin et al. (2012), Wilde-Piórko (2015), Goncharov et al. (2015), Czuba (2017), Selway et al. (2020), Senger et al. (2024)
Deep to shallow crust	~0-40 km	Magnetotelluric data; Seismic reflection data; Gravity and magnetic data	Used for geothermal exploration near Longyearbyen and Ny Ålesund; Provides insights onto the subsurface structures,	Eiken (1985, 1994), Faleide et al. (1988), Olesen et al. (2010), Bælum et al. (2012), Dörr et

		(potential field). GNSS stations;	and outcrop-seismic correlations. Burial and exhumation history of various rocks; Calculate exposure ages and erosion rates	al. (2012), Senger et al. (2013); Blinova et al. (2013); Gjermundsen et al. (2015), Beka et al. (2015, 2016, 2017) Dumais and Brønner (2020)
Surface and uppermost crust (including sediments)	~0-10 km	GNSS stations; Apatite fission track; Cosmogenic nucleides/exposure dating Heat flow and thermal conductivity; outcropping geology	Quaternary geology and surface outcrops. Recent and ongoing uplift, mostly located in western Svalbard. Onshore and offshore data. Heat flow measured offshore Svalbard increases from 80mW/m ² near the continental slope to >300 mW/m ² along the mid-ocean spreading zones	Crane et al. (1991), Okay and Crane (1993), Geissler et al. (2014), Dumke et al. (2016), Klitzke et al. (2016), Grad and Majorowicz (2020), Kierulf et al. (2022b, a) Senger et al. 2023b)

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Appendix 4 – Data packages

The data packages described below can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14216541>

Data package ADP1 – QGIS data package

QGIS data package with a QGIS projects and a selection of key geological and geophysical data in Svalbard (see table AT3 in Senger et al. 2024a). Package includes navigational files of the available geophysical data in Svalbard.

Data package ADP2 – GPlates data package

GPlates data package including the global GeoData data set by Zahirovic (2023) and corresponding publications. Relevant data was added to the project, and the full data set is included for further personalisation by the user. The geological map (Dallmann 2015) and various geophysical data as described in data package ADP1 were also included.

Data package ADP3 – Thermochronology data compilation

Example data set of Apatite fission track data from Svalbard compiled in .csv and NET-CDF format as a showcase for thematic data harvesting and the still existing mismatch between the NET-CDF formatting and the heterogenous nature of geological data.

Data compiled by Cornelia Spiegel, adapted by Fenna Ammerlaan.

Data from: Blythe and Kleinspehn (1998); Dörr et al. (2012, 2019b, a), Schaaf et al. (2021), Japsen et al. (2023), Meier et al. (2024)

Data package ADP4 – Reference collection

Zotero RDF and Bibtext file of the collection of references used in both the main text and appendix. This collection contains the key publications of both geological and geophysical work done in Svalbard and can be imported in other reference management systems.

Data package ADP5 – Research in Svalbard portal and google scholar data

Data set used for the analysis of the geological research done in Svalbard as discussed in section 2.1 and illustrated in Figure 2. Data retrieved from Google Scholar (<https://scholar.google.com/>) and from the Research in Svalbard database (RiS; <https://www.researchinsvalbard.no/>).

Figure AF1: Coverage map of various geological and geophysical data points acquired in Svalbard. Data is available through the QGIS data package and relevant publications can be found in the complementary table AT6.

Digital only appendix:

Appendix 4 – Data packages (digital only)

Table AT3: Data sources of the QGIS package elements.

Data	Source
Thermochronology data compilation (see also ADP3)	Blythe and Kleinspehn (1998); Dörr et al. (2012, 2019b, a), Schaaf et al. (2021), Japsen et al. (2023), Meier et al. (2024)
Svalbox: location of type section sedimentary logs, 360 images, 2D seismics, boreholes	http://portal.svalbox.no e.g., Senger et al. (2019, 2021), Betlem et al. (2023), Horota et al. (2024)
Research in Svalbard: geological fieldwork locations	https://researchinsvalbard.no/ , see also ADP5
Geoscience Atlas maps (geology, paleogeography, resources, structural, geophysical etc.)	Digitized from Dallmann (2015)
Earthquake locations	Pirli et al. (2013), U.S. Geological Survey (2023)
Basemap and various geological maps	Norwegian Polar Institute https://geodata.npolar.no/ https://toposvalbard.npolar.no/
NGU gravity and magnetic compilations	Olesen et al. (2010)
Seismic refraction profile locations	Ritzmann and Jokat (2003), Ritzmann et al. (2004), Czuba et al. (2008), Aarseth et al. (2017)
Various geophysical data portals	BGR: https://arctic.bgr.de/mapapps4/resources/apps/arktis/index.html?lang=en AWI: https://maps.awi.de/awimaps/projects/public/?cu=geophysics_arctic#home NGU: https://geo.ngu.no/geoscienceportalopen/Results?bookmark=0bf79eb071474cd7a92240d4360b84db

Figure AF2: Overview of where geological fieldwork was done according to the Research in Svalbard (RiS) database. Data points shown are also available in the digital QGIS data.

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Appendix 5 - Overview of relevant data repositories for geoscientists working in Svalbard

Table AT4: Relevant thematic and discipline-neutral repositories of geoscientific data.

Repository or database	URL/Reference	Geoscientific data from Svalbard included?	Harvested by SIOS?
Global thematic databases			
Zircon U-Th-Pb global Geochron dataset	Wu et al. (2023)	yes	no
Global geochronological database	http://geochron.org/	yes	no
Global palaeomagnetic library	https://paleomagnetism.org/library/ Koymans et al. (2020)	no	no
USGS Geochronological and Thermochronological data	Hillenbrand et al. (2023) https://doi.org/10.5066/P9RZNPIF	no	no
The Global Heat Flow Database	http://ihfc-iugg.org/products/global-heat-flow-database https://doi.org/10.5880/fidgeo.2024.014	yes	no
Non-thematic data repositories			
PANGAEA (AWI-managed data repository)	https://www.pangaea.de/	yes	Yes for selected datasets, though this may become more dynamic in the future.
Zenodo (CERN-funded data repository)	https://zenodo.org/	yes	no
Arctic Data Archive System (Japanese data archive)	https://ads.nipr.ac.jp/	yes	yes

	http://arcticdata.met.no/	yes	yes
Arctic Data Centre (Norwegian Meteorological Institute)			
	http://arcticnode.dta.cnr.it/cnr/index.php	yes	yes
Italian Arctic Data Center (National Research Council of Italy)			
	https://ppdb.us.edu.pl/	yes	yes
Polish Polar DataBase (University of Silesia)			
	http://ebas.nilu.no/	yes	yes
EBAS (NILU)			
	http://www.nmdc.no/	yes	yes
Norwegian Marine Data Centre (Institute of Marine Research)			
	http://data.npolar.no/	yes	yes
Norwegian Polar Data Centre (Norwegian Polar Institute)			
	https://archive.sigma2.no/	Yes, for example large digital outcrop models such as Festningen (Betlem and Senger 2022).	Not yet but soon. NIRD RDA is represented in the SIOS data management system working group
Norwegian Infrastructure for Research Data Research Data Archive (Funded by Research Council of Norway)			

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Table AT5 - Summary of the main links of selected SIOS core data to the geosphere

SIOS core data	Link to geosphere
SCD 1.1. WIND SPEED	Topographic control
SCD 1.2. WIND DIRECTION	Topographic control
SCD 1.14. CARBON DIOXIDE	Natural release, carbon capture and storage
SCD 1.17. METHANE	Natural release, controlled by subsurface geology, energy source
SCD 2.1. GLACIER MASS BALANCE	Topographic and climatic control
SCD 2.2. GLACIER ELEVATION	Topographic and climatic control
SCD 2.5. ACTIVE LAYER	Topographic, climatic and heat flow control
SCD 2.6. PERMAFROST	Topographic, climatic and heat flow control. Characterization by various geophysical techniques and drilling (LYBCO2 DH8).
SCD 2.7. GROUND ICE	Topographic, climatic and heat flow control. Characterization by various geophysical techniques and drilling (LYBCO2 DH8).
SCD 4.2. SEA LEVEL RISE	Absolute vs relative sea level rise when land uplift is accounted for.
SCD 4.3. OCEAN CURRENTS	Bathymetric control on the circulation patterns (e.g., opening of Fram Strait)
SCD 4.4. SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE	Past global climate change, for instance during mass extinctions.

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Appendix 7 – Heterogeneous geoscientific data sets

Table AT6: Categorization of geoscientific data utilized in Svalbard. The assigned categories illustrate the different data sets in the context of their category, data format, coverage and comments. The assigned data contacts from the authors can provide additional guidance about the specific data types.

Main category	Category	Text section (2.3, 2.4)	Data type/Sub-category	Data format	Data format (recommended for data sharing machines)	Data coverage (global vs Arctic vs regional vs local)	Dimensionality (0D, 1D, 2D, 3D, 4D)	Qualitative vs quantitative	Depth aspect	Time aspect	Date/time of data collection	Comment	Data provider / Data contact	Dataset URL or reference to data paper
Field geology (6.1)	Sampling	2.3	Sample location and storage. Physical rock samples	Physical rock material	N/A	local	0D	Quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Sample location and purpose Ideally linked to sedimentary log	Kim Senger	Norwegian Polar Institute repository (Myhre et al. 2020) German National Polar Sample Archive (BGR 2024a) University-internal repositories NHM
		2.3	Fossils from Arctic Collections	Physical sample	N/A	Local to Arctic	0D	Qualitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Sample location and purpose Ideally linked to sedimentary log	Jørn Hurum	Nakrem et al. 2023
		2.3, 2.4	Thermochronological data	.xlsx	JSON/ncdf	Local to Arctic	0D, 1D	Quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Apatite (U-Th)/He Apatite Fission Track Zircon (U-Th)/He Zircon Fission Track Muscovite Ar/Ar	Cornelia Spiegel-Behnke	Dallmeyer et al. 1990; Blythe and Kleinspehn 1998; Manecki et al. 1998; Dörr et al. 2012, 2013, 2019b, a; Barnes and Schneider 2019; Schneider et al. 2019; Schaaf et al. 2021; Japsen et al. 2023; Meier et al. 2024
		2.3, 2.4	Geochronological data (U-Pb, Pb-Pb, Re-Os)	.xlsx	JSON/ncdf	Local to Arctic	0D	Quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Absolute dating technique U-Pb of magmatic bodies, ash layers, and metamorphic units	Anna Sartell, Jaroslaw Majka	Gee et al. 1995; Johansson et al. 2001, 2002, 2004, 2005; Tebenkov et al. 2002; Myhre et al. 2008; Corfu et al. 2013; Midtkandal et al. 2016; Jones et al. 2017; Koglin et al. 2022; Park et al. 2024
		2.3, 2.4	Geochronological data (Ar-Ar/K-Ar)	.xlsx	JSON/ncdf	Local to Arctic	0D	Quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Absolute dating technique	Anna Sartell, Jaroslaw Majka	Gayer et al. 1966; Burov et al. 1977; Vincenz et al. 1981; Birkenmajer et al. 2010; Nejbort et al. 2011; Polteau et al. 2016; Estrada et al. 2024
		2.3	Oxygen and carbon isotopes	.xlsx	JSON/ncdf	local	0D, 1D	Quantitative	Surface or borehole	varies	varies	Proxies for palaeoclimate	Valentin Zuchuat, Aleksandra	Matysik et al., 2017; Jelby et al. 2020, 2025

						es					Smyrak-Sikora		
	2.3	Rock-Eval	.xlsx	JSON/n etcdf	local	0D, 1D	quan- tita- tive	Surface or borehol- es	varies	varies	Evaluation of source rock quality	Snorre Olaussen	van Koeverden et al. 2011; Marshall et al. 2015; Koevoets et al. 2016, 2019; Abay et al. 2017, 2022; Uguna et al. 2017; Nicolaisen et al. 2019; Jelby et al. 2020; Janocha et al. 2024
	2.3	Vitrinite reflectance	.xlsx	JSON/n etcdf	local	0D, 1D	quan- tita- tive	Surface or borehol- es	varies	varies	Thermal history, coal characterization	Snorre Olaussen	Throndsen 1982; Abdullah et al. 1988; Orheim et al. 2007; Janocha et al. 2024
	2.3	Elemental composition XRF/XRD	.xlsx	JSON/n etcdf	local	0D, 1D	quan- tita- tive	Surface or borehol- es	varies	varies	Chemostratigraphy	Snorre Olaussen	Koevoets et al. 2016, 2019; Wesenlund et al. 2022
	2.4	Detrital zircon provenance	.xlsx	JSON/n etcdf	Local - regio- nal	0D	quan- tita- tive	Surface or borehol- es	varies	varies	Sediment provenance	Cornelia Spiegel- Behnke	Pettersson et al. 2009, 2010; Petersen et al. 2016; Bazarnik et al. 2019; Wala et al. 2021; Anfinson et al. 2022; Klausen et al. 2022
	2.3	Geochemical data	.xlsx	JSON/n etcdf	regio- nal	0D	quan- tita- tive	Surface or borehol- es	varies	varies	Major and trace elements	Anna Sartell	Bailey and Rasmussen 1997; Sushchevskaya et al. 2009; Nejbert et al. 2011; Ottesen 2015; Jones et al. 2016; Koglin et al. 2022; Estrada et al. 2024
	2.4	Palaeomagnet- ic data	.xlsx	JSON/n etcdf	local	0D	quan- tita- tive	Surface or borehol- es	varies	varies	Magnetostratigra- phy and constraining plate tectonic movement	Krzysztof Michalski	Vincenz and Jelenska 1985; Halvorsen 1989; Michalski and Lewandowski 2004; Maloof et al. 2006; Hounslow et al. 2008; Michalski et al. 2012, 2017, 2023; Dudzisz et al. 2016, 2018; Burzyński et al. 2017; Michalski 2018; Zhang et al. 2021
	2.4	Xenoliths from upper mantle	.xlsx	JSON/n etcdf	local	1D/ 2D	quan- tita- tive	Lower crust/up- per mantle	varies	varies	Xenoliths within Neogene/Quatern- ary volcanic rocks	Sverre Planke	Griffin et al. 2012
Sedimento	2.3	Sedimentary	.jpg/.png/.ti	CF-	local	1D	quali	Surface	varies	varies	Observations and	Sten-	Dallmann 1999; Midtkandal et al.

log/stratigraphic logging		log	ff	NetCDF			quantitative	Surface or boreholes			descriptions of sedimentary units, plus sampling	Andreas Grundvåg	2008; Ahlborn and Stemmerik 2015; Olausen et al. 2018; Rismyhr et al. 2019; Grundvåg et al. 2020; Sorento et al. 2020; Helland-Hansen and Grundvåg 2021
Structural mapping	2.4	Scanlines, structural data, restorations	.txt/.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	local	2D	quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Mapping of fractures and faults	Kei Ogata	Ogata et al. 2014; Piepjohn et al. 2016; Koglin et al. 2022
Field sketches/field notebooks	2.3, 2.4	Observations, field data	.jpg/.png/.tif	CF-NetCDF		2D	qualitative	Surface	varies	varies	Observations	Aleksandra Smyrak-Sikora	Arctic Viewer (BGR 2024b)
Digital field notebooks	2.3, 2.4	Georeferenced images, notes, orientation data	.mve, kmz, .csv		local	0D to 2D	Quantitative, qualitative	Surface	varies	varies	Observations and documentation	Kim Senger	Senger and Nordmo 2021
Field photographs	2.3, 2.4	Images	.jpeg	CF-NetCDF	local	2D	qualitative	Surface	varies	varies	Observations	all	
Field mapping	2.3, 2.4	Geological maps	.shp, .geotiff	netcdf/geosJSON	regional	2D	qualitative	Surface	varies	varies	Observations, sampling	NPI	Dallmann 2015
Field mapping	2.3, 2.4	Fault maps	.shp	netcdf/geosJSON	regional	2D	quantitative	Surface	varies	varies	Observations, structural focus	NPI	Major and Nagy 1972; Braathen et al. 1999; Dallmann 2015
Digital geology	2.3, 2.4	Digital outcrop models (SfM)	.obj and others	CF-NetCDF	local-regional	3D	quantitative	Surface	varies	varies	3D models of outcrops	Peter Betlem, Kim Senger	Betlem et al. 2023, 2024
	2.3, 2.4	Digital outcrop models (Lidar)	LiDAR	CF-NetCDF	local-regional	3D	quantitative	Surface	varies	varies	3D models of outcrops	Peter Betlem, Kim Senger	Senger et al. 2013; Smyrak-Sikora et al. 2021
	2.3, 2.4	Photospheres	.jpg, .jpeg	CF-NetCDF	Aerial Local	2.5D	qualitative	surface	varies	varies	2D photography data visualised in 3D.	Rafel Horota	Horota et al. 2023, 2024

		2.3, 2.4	Digital sample/drill core models	.obj	CF-NetCDF	local	3D		Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	3d models of drill cores	Peter Betlem	Betlem et al. 2020	
Boreholes and drill cores (6.2)	Borehole data (scientific)	2.3, 2.4	Drill cores	Physical material	N/A	local	1D	qualitative	Boreholes	varies	varies		Kim Senger, Sverre Planke	CO2 wells and exploration wells: Olausen et al. 2019; Senger et al. 2019; DD-1 core sedimentary log: appendix of Zuchuat et al. 2020; Senger et al. 2024a	
		2.3, 2.4	Wireline logs	.xlsx, .las	CF-NetCDF	local	1D	quantitative	Boreholes	varies	varies		Kim Senger	Koevoets et al. 2019; Olausen et al. 2019; Grundvåg et al. 2019	
		2.3, 2.4	Technical reports	.pdf, .doc			local	1D	qualitative	Boreholes	varies	varies		Kim Senger	Senger et al. 2022, 2024a
		2.3, 2.4	Analyses on drill cores	.xlsx		CF-NetCDF		1D	quantitative	Boreholes	varies	varies	Oxygen and carbon isotopes Geochemistry Trace elements Geochronology Rock-Eval / vitrinite reflectance Elemental composition XRF/XRD MSCL Photographs Well tops isotopes	Aleksandra Smyrak-Sikora	Grundvåg et al. 2014; Dörr et al. 2019a; DD-1 core, raw XRF scan: appendix of Zuchuat et al. 2020; Senger et al. 2024a
		2.3, 2.4	Biostratigraphy							Boreholes and outcrops	varies		Most commonly studied fossils include dinocysts, foraminifera, and ammonites. A database with biostratigraphic data does not exist yet. Majority of the older publication	Kasia K. Sliwinska	Cenozoic: Manum 1960; Bjærke 1978; Feyling-Hanssen and Ulleberg 1984; Matthiessen 1986; Manum and Thronsen 1986; Kvaček 1994; Nagy 2005; Golovneva 2010; Nagy et al. 2013 Mesozoic: Spath 1921; Blüthgen 1936;

does have only presence/absence or results of semiquantitative analysis provided

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Palaeozoic:Vigran 1964; Allen 1967; Nakrem et al. 1992; Mangerud and Konieczny 1993; Buggisch et al. 2001; Luppold 2001; Błażejowski et al. 2006; Błażejowski 2009; Berry and Marshall 2015; Kröger et al. 2017; Lopes et al. 2019, 2021

Borehole data (commercial)	2.3, 2.4	Drill cores	Physical material	CF-NetCDF?	1D	qualitative	Boreholes	varies	SNSK, Trust Artikugol, various petroleum companies	Senger et al. 2023a
	2.3, 2.4	Wireline logs	.xlsx, .las	CF-NetCDF	1D	quantitative	Boreholes	varies	Kim Senger	Senger et al. 2022
	2.3, 2.4	Technical reports	.pdf	CF-NetCDF	1D	qualitative	Boreholes	varies	Kim Senger, Snorre Olausen	Senger et al. 2022
	2.4	Heat flow data	.xls	JSON/netcdf	1D		Surface or boreholes	varies	Kim Senger, Alexander Minakov	Global Heatflow Database, Senger et al. 2023b

Geophysics (6.3)	Magnetoteluric data	2.4	Deep geophysics	.segY	CF-NetCDF		2D	quantitative	Surface to tens of kms	varies	Alexander Minakov	Beka et al. 2016; Selway et al. 2020
	Shallow geophysical profiles (ERT, GPR etc.)	2.4	Shallow geophysics	.segY	CF-NetCDF		2D	quantitative	10s to 100s of meters		Kim Senger	Ignatiuk et al. 2023; Pace et al. 2024
	Gravity data	2.4	Geophysics	.xlsx	CF-NetCDF	Local to regional	1D (on shore) 2D (off shore)	quantitative	km-scale		UNIS/NGU Kim Senger Marie-Andree Dumais	Olesen et al. 2010; Senger et al. in press
	Magnetic data (ship-based)	2.4	Profile-based geophysics	.xlsx	CF-NetCDF	local	2D	quantitative	Ms to kms		Kim Senger	Senger et al. 2013
	Magnetic data (aerial)	2.4	Profile-based geophysics	.xlsx	CF-NetCDF	regional	2D	quantitative	Ms to kms		Marie-Andree Dumais, Antonia Ruppel	Olesen et al. 2010; Dumais and Brönnert 2020
	Global seismic tomography	2.4	Deep geophysics			global	2D/ 3D	quantitative	Crustal-mantle scale		Wolfram Geissler, Grace Shephard	Schaeffer and Lebedev 2013; Struijk et al. 2018
	Seismic data (2D)	2.4	Profile-based geophysics on- and offshore	.segY		Local to regional	2D	quantitative	Uppermost ca 5 km	Shallow vs deep focus Industry vs academia Onshore vs offshore	Wolfram Geissler, Alexander Minakov	Eiken 1985; Johansen et al. 2011; Bælum et al. 2012; Rossi et al. 2018 Data example Pangea: Weigelt and Geissler 2024
	Active seismicity	2.4	Deep to shallow geophysics			Local to regional	0D	quantitative	Surface to epicentre		Alexander Minakov	NORSAR 1971; Köhler et al. 2020; International Seismological Centre 2024

Remote sensing (6.4)	Digital terrain model(s)	2.3, 2.4	Surface		CF-NetCDF	regional	3D	quantitative	surface	Modern and historical models provided	NPI	Norwegian Polar Institute 2014; Porter et al. 2023
	Satellite imagery	2.3, 2.4	Surface	.jpg2000	CF-NetCDF / SAFE / ZARR	regional	3D	quantitative	surface		NPI	Norwegian Polar Institute 2023
	Oblique aerial images (historic)	2.3, 2.4	Surface			regional	2D	quantitative	surface		NPI	toposvalbard.npolar.no
	Bathymetry	2.4	Ocean bottom morphology		CF-NetCDF	regional	3D	quantitative	surface		IBCAO	IBCAO (Jakobsson et al. 2012) Statens kartverket
	Satellite-derived gravity data	2.4	Deep geophysics			global	2D	quantitative	km-scale		Alexander Minakov	Mémin et al. 2011
	Satellite-derived magnetic data	2.4	Deep geophysics			global	2D	quantitative	km-scale		Alexander Minakov	Olsen et al. 2017; Sabaka et al. 2020.
	inSAR data	2.4	Surface deformation			regional	4D	quantitative	surface		Kim Senger	Rouyet et al. 2024
	GNSS	2.4	Surface deformation			local	4D	quantitative	surface		Halfdan Kierulf	Kierulf et al. 2022
Data integration and data products (6.5)	Palaeogeographic maps	2.3	Maps with a temporal component			regional	2D	qualitative	surface		Sten-Andreas Grundvåg	Smelror et al. 2009; Dallmann 2015
	Digital	2.4	Temporal	Gplates		Regio	4D	qua	surface		Grace	Shephard et al. 2013

plate tectonic reconstructions					nal to global	ntitative			Shephard	
Geological cross-sections	2.4	Profiles			Local to regional	2D qualitative	km-scale			Dallmann 2015 + publications
Sub-ice topography	2.4			CF-NetCDF		3D quantitative	km-scale			Fürst et al. 2018
(educational) Thematic data packages	2.3, 2.4	Integrated data sets	.shp, .jpg, .jpeg, .tiff, .obj			0D-4D both	varies		Rafael Horota	Horota et al. 2023; Senger et al. 2024b
Publications	2.3, 2.4	Thematically diverse				0D-4D both	varies		Snorre Olausen	Steel and Worsley 1984; Harland 1997; Dallmann 1999, 2015; Worsley 2008 Faleide et al. 2024; Lundschieen et al. 2024; Tsikalas et al. 2024; Olausen et al. 2024; Smelror et al. 2024
Pre-loaded data packages	2.3, 2.4	QGIS	QGIS project			0D-4D both	varies		Fenna Ammerlaan	Appendix ADP1, this contribution
	2.3, 2.4	GPlates	GPlates project			0D-4D both	varies		Fenna Ammerlaan	Appendix ADP2, this contribution

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